

Covid-19 Lockdown and Critical Perspectives on Online Education

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Abstract

As soon as the Government of India said "lockdown," many places, including schools, shut -the UNESCO going students, The Indian government decided to start online classes to compensate for learning loss, but it also brought many challenges to society, particularly in terms of learning loss, a lack of resources, a lack of familiarity with technological gadgets, and digital classroom attendance. These are some reasons, if we give attention to other factors related to educational systems, there are many areas of concern that require close attention. This paper attempts to highlight the impact of COVID-19 on learning loss and how the educational system responded to compensate for this with newer mechanisms.

Key words: COVID-19, Traditional Teaching, Online Learning, Learning Loss.

Introduction

The COVID-19 revealed a number of critical issues for us to address. One of these crucial areas of concern is the UNESCO, shutdown of educational institutions and its impact on students of all levels. If we look at the data provided by UNESCO, it stated that over 800 million learners from around the world have been affected, 1 in 5 learners cannot attend school, 1 in 4 cannot attend higher education classes, and over 102 countries have ordered nationwide school closures while 11 have implemented localised school closure.[1] The data provides clear picture of learning loss and difficulties in resuming the traditional practices of teaching and learning. Education plays an important role in the life of school, college and university going students. When it comes to the learning aspect, still globally the physical mode of teaching is in practice as a traditional model of learning. In the scenario of Covid-19 this very traditional model of teaching and learning got disrupted. UNDP stated that "With more than 1.4 billion children's schools closed indefinitely, new technology-based measures are being used to continue the learning process.[2] This new model of teaching and learning brought many challenges in rendering the services. It is important to discuss that the challenges are not only impacting students but equally the huge adverse impact was on teachers. Dealing with newer modes of teaching along with Covid-19 management and lockdown of primary services added a huge burden on both students and teachers.

To deal with learning loss the immediate launch of online teaching model generated curiosity, excitement and also anxiety among teachers and students. It is not that we as people of modern world were not aware of gadgets use but for purpose of education and official use through online platforms exposed the world to newer world , which was the digital world. The physical exchange of gestures, expressions and interpersonal communication were replaced by online communication, distanced face to face interaction with consciousness of creating official ambience at home. Out of all the biggest challenge was to resume the teaching learning practice. Starting classes in time, exchange of notes and readings, clarifying on doubts, but the major challenge was to generate interest in online learning. No doubt with the help of technology we could resume the services immediately, but access to internet, gadgets and and space to ensure timely services were biggest challenge. With all of this we entered in new technological or digital world with any advance knowledge and preparedness.

Use of technology

The market utilizes the Covid-19 situation in the best way to fill up the gap of traditional mode of teaching. Also global society took this digital market expansion in a positive way. The UNDP report cited that, "This positive development from the recent technological revolution supports the resilience to shocks in education, a key human development dimension. So, what is the effective out-of-school rate after considering these efforts? Adjusting the percentage of primary, school-age children facing school closures to account for households with access to the Internet—and opportunity to continue structured learning sheds some light on this question"[3] But this market expansion for creating digital spaces could not address all problems which arise out of closure of educational systems. For example in India, the schools are one of the important unit for social learning, cognitive enhancement and maintaining nutritional needs of school going children. The mid day meal programme, and supporting girl child education are most important schemes of India. With the closure of school the burden of undernutrition and gender inequality again affected children of marginalised sections adversely[4].

Though use of technology and digital equipment was the only way to fill up the gap of learning loss , this came up with a huge cost. In India the digital device ownership difference increased with intersectionality of gender, class and region. The media reported that, "though schools are closed, students are attending their classes through various education initiatives like online classrooms and radio programs. Though it is a good thing that is happening but on the other side, there are lots of students who don't have the resources to attend the online classes. Many students are struggling to obtain the gadgets required for online classes [5]

In the above context, it is important to deliberate and discuss how different educational institutions have resumed teaching and learning services, adopted the digital world, faced challenges in day-to-day online classes, and protected the best interests of the students.

Case illustration of the Department of Social Work- Teaching-learning experience during the COVID-19 pandemic

Teaching in a online classroom

The Department of Social Work followed the rules set by the Indian government and the University of Delhi. The department opted for online teaching through Google Meet and Zoom. The university had provided a free G-Suite account to all the faculty members. The respective faculty members created a Google Classroom for online teaching and learning. The teacher of each course made a single Google Meet link that all students could use to join the class at the same time. All of the course's instructions, timetable, teaching schedule, and readings were uploaded to the classroom to make sure that teaching and learning went smoothly and in sync with each other. This was a very good platform, and it was very well liked by the student community. The only problem was that students who couldn't connect to the internet well had to deal with interruptions during class.

Fieldwork practicum and supervision: Fieldwork is one of the most important parts of learning how to be a social worker. It is considered core signatory pedagogy. The Department of Social Work at Delhi University did not compromise with fieldwork. It was decided by the department that keeping in view of students best interest the online platform will be utilised , and fieldwork practicum would be done online. Each student was allotted a supervisor(faculty member), and the supervisors used Google Meet to set up a group meeting with their own supervisors. First, they found out where the students were staying and how long they would be there. Then, the students and the faculty supervisor worked together to find an agency in each student's residential area or nearby area of their stay, the supervisor instructed the students to contact NGOs/govt agencies to get permission to do fieldwork. The supervisor would get the director's and contact person's information, and then communication was made through email or the phone. After the first two meetings, everyone agreed on the tasks and assignments, which were then put into a term/action plan for the fieldwork. The online monitoring system made fieldwork report submission easy. The students used to submit their reports via email or the Google Classroom directory. By using online platforms supervisors were able to track their progress, understanding their day-to-day challenges.

The case illustrations of a few students: There were 3 students placed under authors supervision during the COVID-19 pandemic: one was staying at Gujler (MP), one was at Surat (Gujarat), and another was at Yavatmal (Maharashtra). Three states and three different locations were involved, but their fieldwork practice was very well coordinated through online teaching and learning. These students were given tasks and online assignments to visit COVID-affected families and find out what they needed. They were also told very clearly to choose the local guide given to them by district officials as an example of what was expected of them during the pandemic. Lastly, the students got a very realistic and grounded understanding of the locality and the families that were affected during the pandemic. They also helped some families, especially those in slum areas, get the rations, essential

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medicines, and other help they needed from local organizations. Families whose loved ones died because of COVID were given counseling or psychiatric help.

Use of WhatsApp Groups in Teaching and Learning

The Use of WhatsApp Groups During the pandemic, the use of WhatsApp for teaching and learning was very systematic. The faculty advisors used to write common instructions on the WhatsApp group, and students used to write questions, challenges, and difficulties, and their insights and learning were sometimes shared through this platform. Even the individual and group conferences were coordinated through this platform.

Student Seminar: The most important parts of the fieldwork practicum is the student seminar. This activity is designed in such a way that students should get first-hand experience writing an academic paper based on their fieldwork and making a presentation on the same in a group. During the pandemic, this activity was also coordinated in an online mode. The respective coordinators started this process at the beginning of the semester. The guidelines included tentative deadlines. They were also given to each faculty supervisor to help with finalizing the topic, submitting the abstract, submitting the first and second drafts, and submitting the final draft of the paper. Once the coordinators received all the written papers, almost nine groups were created for the paper presentation. Three faculty supervisors and their students merged into one group. All of the faculty members were given the detailed rules and instructions, and they used the Google Meet platform to give group presentations. For each group, one faculty supervisor was chosen to be the coordinator. This person was in charge of making a link with other faculty members and their students and spreading the word. Finally, all of the students gave their presentations, and the different groups agreed on a date to confirm the minutes. Then, the seminar minutes were approved.

Block placement: This is another important component of the M.A. in the Social Work program at DSSW. During the pandemic, this activity was again well coordinated during online teaching. The objective of this block placement is that the students should get first-hand work experience in an NGO or project/program setting to improve their skills and competencies. But because of the pandemic and the lockdown challenge, students couldn't be placed in a physical mode, so a decision was made at a staff council meeting that block placement would be carried out in an online mode. These students shall be placed in the Nodal Center for COVID-19, which was created at the DSSW to coordinate different activities during the pandemic. Two phase model was created for online block placement. Each phase consists of a 15 day duration for their block. The goal of the common task was to visit at least five families in their own homes and neighborhoods. To do a survey of those families and also to write a case study on how these families were affected during the pandemic. These forms were also created for a while using Google Forms tools. The data was also captured through these forms, and an analysis was also made based on the information provided by the student. The daily report writing and submission were done in another Google Form. The students submitted their daily and comprehensive report through online mode only after two successive blocks, and the viva voce was organized at the end of the semester.

Critical Issues and Challenges

The biggest challenge was to adopt a new work style and that too with an online platform. The innovative ideas to organise class, contact with students, online supervision and to accept limitations of the online medium was not only thought provoking but also forced the world to enter the online or digital world. The choice to say no was not available and by anyhow teachers manage to run the systems. The population who was privileged was really lucky to enjoy and explore newer ways of communication, teaching and learning. They really are able to get the benefit of this innovative idea to be in a new digital world to get associated with each other. But shockingly the majority was out of this privilege, especially marginalized such as poor, women, and rural areas population. The big digital divide is the challenge in a situation when world is pushing all physical boundaries and entering into new digital spaces (G20, 2017). In the context of marginalised those, who were struggling hard to get into mainstream, again pushed further in marginalised zones.

Conclusion

The Covid-19 Pandemic demonstrated that human beings have the potential to utilise any difficult situation for their best interest. At the same time human beings are also vulnerable due to structural issues, infrastructural limitations and lack of support. But with the help of critical and innovative thinking the current challenges can be overcome. The teaching learning practices continued throughout pandemic lockdown time, at initial level there were many obstacles, hesitations and limitations but gradually teachers across the region at all levels demonstrated

that they can put best efforts to face their personal and professional challenges. The major challenge was in the form of lack of infrastructural support, electronic gadgets, internet connectivity and electricity connections. In this situation we cannot say that we are completely equipped with all the resources, but with ample availability of human potential the availability of online platforms and medium tools to access online platforms are really crucial from both student and teachers point of view. The gender aspect in the context of equal opportunity on an equitable level is crucial in the Indian scenario. More efforts with appropriate strategies are required to maintain gender parity in the educational sector.

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